

Balochistan's Trophy Hunting Program Promoting Conservation and Community Development

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Abstract

This study assesses the Trophy Hunting Programme in Balochistan its practice, impacts in biodiversity improvement within six community-based conservancies in Balochistan namely 1) Torghar Community Game Reserve, 2) Dureji Community Game Reserve, 3) Shahnoorani Community Game Reserve, 4) Taloband Community Game Reserve, 5) Phore Community Game Reserve and 6) Baran Lakh Community Game Reserve, Pakistan. The study focuses on the harvest of five ungulate species (Suleiman Markhor, Afghan Urial, Blandford Urial, Sind Ibex, and Kennion Gazelle). Data analysis explores species quotas allocated by the CITES management authority, revenue generation, and the program's impact on local communities. The analysis of data in this study reveals that in Trophy Hunting Season 2021-22 overall quota for Balochistan was 44 Nos., while in Trophy Hunting Season 2022-23 it was increased upto 56 Trophies and in Trophy Hunting Season 2023-24 it has jumped upto allocation of 80 trophies to the province which indicates the increase in the population size of targeted species in all the notified conservancies, moreover, the trophy hunting season 2023-24 was highly successful, with the Suleiman Markhor fetching the world's highest bid of Rs. 0.245 Million (US Dollars) and generating a total Revenue as Rs. 455,222,835/- (Four Hundred Fifty-five Million Two Hundred Twenty-two Thousand Eight Hundred Thirty-five). Based on these results, the study recommends: Strategically expanding trophy hunting opportunities with meticulous consideration of new target species and geographic areas, Establishing a dedicated Trophy Hunting Endowment Fund to channel revenue towards wildlife habitat enhancement and community development initiatives, Implementing supplementary projects within the conservancies to address climate change mitigation and zoonotic disease control and Utilizing online bidding platforms to streamline the process and enhance accessibility for international hunters. Besides, the evaluation of Historical data of the study suggests a positive correlation between trophy hunting and population growth of targeted ungulate species within the conservancies. This research also contributes to the ongoing discourse on the viability of trophy hunting as a sustainable conservation strategy and its potential to generate socioeconomic benefits for local communities.

Keywords: *Laser Physics; Multimedia Technologies; Teaching Methods; Digital Modeling, Individualized Education; Adobe Flash CS3; Java Programs*

Introduction

According to Lindsey et al. (2007), trophy hunting is the most lucrative kind of animal exploitation. It is also a substantial and expanding industry in a number of regions throughout the globe, particularly in Africa. In the practice of trophy hunting, a hunter would often kill the biggest animal in a particular region in exchange for a substantial sum of money that is then donated to those who are responsible for conservation, such as an individual, a community, or a government organization (Frisina, 2000). When a hunter pays a significant price to hunt a large animal in regions that have been designated for the protection of wildlife, this kind of hunting is considered to be a recreational activity. In the late 1990s, trophy hunting became a heavily debated topic in the fields of ethics, biology, and society. This led to a major increase in the amount of attention it received. According to Infield and Namara (2001), it is appropriate to include communities in the sustainable use of natural resources, provided that doing so in a way that is beneficial to the individuals who are involved in the management of the resources. According to Lindsey et al. (2007), these issues constrained the contribution that the sector could provide to conservation efforts. One of the most important things that can be done to protect endangered species is to engage in trophy hunting under supervision. Numerous pieces of data gathered from all around the globe suggest that trophy hunting has successfully led to an increase in the population of endangered animals, which has resulted in the removal of these creatures from the conservation list of endangered species. Across the globe, trophy hunting is a common activity. There are twenty-three nations in Africa that have a large industry that is based on trophy hunting. Trophy hunting is a sporting activity in the Southern and Eastern African countries. However, as regards with the regions of Central and Western Africa, trophy hunting has a close association with several small companies. Each year, R100m is channeled to the South African economy through the trophy hunting activity. As H. Ali et al (2015) report, the trophy hunting industry in Namibia generates approximately US\$25.5 million per annum in economic terms of the country. In those cases when trophy hunting is not a matter of the pursuit of pleasure but of the ideology and mindset which are focused on the human interests and are set above all other considerations, it is considered as unethical. Conversely, it can serve as an efficient conservation strategy for areas that experience high demand for land use (Angula et al., 2018). This would be accomplished by a measuring and evaluation system that is both extensive and precise. As suggested in the study conducted by Crosmary et al. (2015), the risk is low because the money can be allocated for different kinds of conservation objectives and goals.

Community-based trophy hunting programs could bring about economic and ecological benefits that are crucial. These benefits include the financial support given to the upkeep of the rare and endangered animal species and the financial assistance provided to the local communities. The trophy hunt operations in Pakistan and Tajikistan have been able to perform two objectives successfully, although they are based on different models. These goals consist of making the numbers of important wildlife species to be more and also increasing the well-being and income of the community. This strategy should be all-encompassing, comprehensive, and focused on ecosystems as a whole, rather than centering its attention just on a single species. Alongside this, there must be a workable incentive program that encourages biodiversity (which encompasses species, habitats, and ecosystems) and provides advantages to the populations that are located nearby. Rashid et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2011; Muhammad et al., 2019; Rashid et al., 2020). Community-driven trophy hunting projects in Pakistan and Tajikistan are two examples that demonstrate the effectiveness of including local communities in wildlife conservation efforts. These initiatives have been shown to be effective in mountainous regions. This idea has the potential to be replicated in other locations and even farther afield in order to improve biodiversity and provide assistance to local inhabitants.

The country's towering mountains, dense forests, and the varied landscape make Pakistan, which has a land area of 881,913 square kilometers, the home to a diverse array of plant and animal species. Pakistan has got three distinctive biogeographical zones among them, which are the Indo-Malayan,

Palaearctic, and Afro-Tropical areas. Each of these regions harbor their own unique sets of animals. Furthermore, according to Baig and Al-Subaiee (2009), Pakistan is home to four different biomes: the rangeland, the steppe, the forest, and the mountain. The country has mountain ranges that span almost two-thirds of the land, and these mountainous areas are home to a large population of animals. The species list that is given below is the list of the species that have been documented in Pakistan. Lashari et al. (2019) state that there are around 5,000 invertebrate species. Plants, mammals, birds and reptiles constitute a total of 5910, 182, 662 and 174 species, respectively. The birds that migrate through Pakistan in large numbers contribute a major fraction of the total bird population of the country. According to Roberts (1967), they are migratory birds and therefore they come in the winter time. The country which is characterized by its climate, Pakistan has the mix of arid and semi-arid conditions that prevail there. As the conclusion of Lashari et al. in 2019, the park is also a home to a wide range of animals comprising 22 amphibian species, 29 fish species, and 8 butterfly species. It is estimated that there are around 3 thousand different taxonomic groups, which have been cultivated. The participation of the community is essential to the achievement of this goal. The secondary aim of community benefits must be accomplished in order to realize the core purpose of preservation, which is to preserve the environment. About eighty percent of the cash that is created is sent to the local communities. This money is then utilized for a variety of objectives, including the improvement of infrastructure, the provision of interest-free loans to members of the community, the provision of scholarships to students from disadvantaged backgrounds, and the implementation of various community development programs. In order to successfully preserve biodiversity, community-based conservation is a vital component of conservation efforts. "The primary objective is to synchronize local communities and resource users with the objectives of preserving biodiversity and promoting human well-being," according to Salerno et al. (2021).

In Pakistan, trophy hunting for ungulates started in the early 1990s, with a primary emphasis on community-based programs. The community-based trophy hunting program in the Torghar region of Balochistan was established by the Society for Torghar Environmental Protection (STEP), which provides environmental protection services. The revenues that were earned were used to compensate wildlife guards who were employed by the local community in an effort to discourage acts that were considered to be poaching. Within the framework of Resolution Conf. 8.21 in 1992, the Markhor (*Capra falconeri*) was reclassified to CITES Appendix I, which therefore made hunting of this species unacceptable. A annual limit for Markhor trophy hunting was established at the tenth meeting of the Conference of Parties of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES) in 1997. The impressive community-based wildlife management that Pakistan has implemented has resulted in the country being granted a quota of six Markhor on a yearly basis. According to Resolution Conf. 10.15 (Rev. CoP14), the limit was raised to twelve at the CITES CoP12 in response to Pakistan's request. This was done in conformity with previous CoP14 resolutions. Each of Pakistan's three range provinces and territories receives four Markhor from the annual allotment of twelve Markhor. Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Gilgit-Baltistan each get four Markhor from the allocation. The population that is now present in these locations is the primary factor that determines this distribution. CITES Management Authority is the entity responsible for the assignment of quotas on a federal level. A decision is made about the allocation based on the recommendations that are offered by the Scientific Authority. Community-managed conservation zones have been created by the provincial and territorial wildlife authorities within areas that are essential for the species. Local community organizations that have been created in their respective regions explicitly outline the responsibilities that are assigned to local communities. The trophies are then put up for sale via open auctions at the provincial and territorial level once the yearly quotas have been distributed. The process of trophy hunting is controlled by provincial and territorial wildlife authorities in conjunction with local communities. Licensed trophy hunting outfitters are responsible for facilitating the hunting of prize animals. Eighty percent of the cash collected is distributed to local communities, who then utilize that money to support conservation programs that are designed to benefit the community. Wildlife authorities at the provincial and territorial levels work together with local communities to supervise the monitoring of animals, conduct surveys, and vigilantly discover cases of poaching.

In the province of Balochistan, the community-based trophy hunting program has lately expanded to include a number of new local populations. For example, the Torghar Community Game Reserve, the Dureji Community Game Reserve, the Shahnoorani Community Game Reserve, the Taloband Community Game Reserve, the Phore Community Game Reserve, and the Baran Lakh Community Game Reserve are all examples of such reserves. The Afghan Urial, the Blandford Urial, the Sind Ibex, and the Kennion Gazelle are the five additional species of ungulates that call these areas in Pakistan their home. These reserves are situated in Pakistan.

Methodology

This paper adopts mixed-method studies involving the integration of the qualitative and quantitative findings in the research process. It includes data collection, interpretation, and analysis. The primary data for the study was collected from the stakeholders i.e. Balochistan Forest & Wildlife Department, Concerned Communities, Focused Group, District Administration and Hunters. Furthermore, from each stakeholder data was collected from the ten (10) respondents each which comprises total respondent equal to 50 Respondents. For Secondary Data of the study various Research Papers, Documents, Balochistan Wildlife Act 2014 & Rule, 2015 and The Balochistan Wildlife Policy 2020 were gone through.

Result & Discussion

Trophy hunting is used for species conservation and fulfils other additional objectives. Trophy hunting not only conserves particular species, but it also safeguards local economies and cultures. Multifunctionality, in the context of trophy hunting, refers to the idea that all activities associated with trophy hunting have a positive impact on the local community. It serves ecological, social, and economic purposes.

After analysis of collected data from respondents following were identified:

- TORs set for Trophy Hunting in Balochistan

The following TORs are implemented by the Forest & Wildlife Department Balochistan for the Trophy Hunting Programme:

1. Eighty percent (80 %) proceeds of trophy hunting permit for each permit @ USD will be deposited in the bank account of that particular community-based conservancy and twenty percent (20%) of each permit @ USD will be deposited through treasury bank challans, in the Account No. (C-03327) of Government of Balochistan.
2. Depositing of above-mentioned (80 %) trophy hunting permit fees @ USD in the bank account of that particular community-based conservancy up to first week of December, 2023 and (20%) of each permit @ USD through treasury bank challans, in the Account No. (C-03327) of Government of Balochistan.
3. Before hunting the hunter shall obtain “Big Game Shooting License at following rates for each permit from office of the Chief Conservator Wildlife Balochistan.
 - a. Suleiman Markhor @ Rs.25000/- per shooting license/permit,
 - b. Blandford Urial @ Rs.15000/- per shooting license/permit and
 - c. Sindh Ibex @ Rs.5000/- per shooting license/permit.

4. Trophy hunting fee once paid shall not be refundable.

5. The security and safety of hunters, from their arrival to departure from province, as well as other security related clearances/formalities/NOCs shall be the responsibility of outfitters and representative's/office bearers of that particular community-based conservancy, where the trophy hunting is going to takes place. The Balochistan Forest and Wildlife Department will not be responsible for any causality/injury etc. that may happen during the hunting process.

Graphical Representation of Permits Per Year

➤ Status of Trophy Species in Balochistan

Table 1. Status of Trophy Species in Schedules of Balochistan Wildlife (Protection, Preservation, Conservation & Management) Act, 2014

S.No	Local Name	Scientific Name	Schedule
1	Markhor	<i>Capra falconeri</i>	Generally, all three species are of Schedule-III of Protected Animals, but also reflected Schedule-I of Game Animals only during hunting season from 1 st December to 31 st January. However, as per provision of Rule 11(4) of Balochistan Wildlife (Protection, Conservation & Management) Rules, 2015 the Chief Conservator of Forest on recommendation of Conservator Wildlife & National Parks may extend the hunting period up to 31 st March.
2	Urrial	<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	
4	Ibex	<i>Capra aegragrus</i>	

➤ Details of Species with Minimum Fee and Quota for each Provincial Territory

The CITES Management Authority annually allocate a specific quota for following species which is based on survey reports conducted before each season in the conservancies:

Table 2. Details of Species with Minimum Fee and Quota for each Provincial Territory

S#	Name of Species	CITES Appendix	Provincial Territory	Mini Fee	Quota
1	Suleiman Markhor	Appendix-1	Torghar Community Game Reserve	USD80,000-	04
2	Afghan Urial	Appendix-II		USD20,000-	07
3	Blandford's Urial	Appendix-II	Dureiji Community Game Reserve	USD20,000-	12
4	Sindh Ibex	Appendix-III		USD-5000/-	12
5	Blandford's Urial	Appendix-II	Shahnoorani Community Game Reserve	USD20,000-	08
6	Sindh Ibex	Appendix-III		USD-5,000/-	08
7	Blandford's Urial	Appendix-II	Talo Band Community Game Reserve	USD20,000-	05
8	Sindh Ibex	Appendix-III		USD-5,000/-	05
9	Blandford's Urial	Appendix-II	Phore Community Game Reserve	USD20,000-	05

The detail of rates offered by bidders/outfitters in six community-based wildlife conservancies for different ungulate species and their number for trophy hunting season 2023-24 is detailed below:

1. Comparative Statement for Auction of Permits of Trophy Hunting of Markhor & Afghan Urial **Torghar Community** based Conservancy of K. Saifullah for Hunting Season 2023-2024.

i. Suleiman Markhor Permits (04):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	Karakurum Treks & Tours GB	USD80,000/per permit	01	USD-245,500/permit	Highest
2	M/S Zoon Safaris	USD80,000/per permit	01	USD220,000/permit	2 nd Highest
3	M/S Zoon Safaris	USD80,000/per permit	01	USD218,000/permit	3 rd Highest
4	M/S Adventure Pakistan	USD80,000/per permit	01	USD210,000/permit	4 th Highest

ii. Afghan Urial Permits (07):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S M/S Zoon Safaris	USD20,000/permit	01	USD21,000/permit	Highest
2	Karakurum Treks & Tours GB	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20300/ permit	2 nd Highest
3	M/S Adventure Pakistan	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20100/ permit	3 rd Highest
4	M/S Shikar Safari Pakistan	USD20,000/permit	02	USD20,000/permit	4 th Highest
5	M/S Himalaya Nature Tours	USD20,000/permit	02	USD20,000/permit	4 th Highest

2. Comparative Statement for Auction of Permits of Trophy Hunting of Balochistan Urial, Sindh Ibex & Kennion Gazelle in Dureiji Community based Conservancy of Lasbela for Hunting Season 2023-2024.

i. Blandford/Balochistan Urial (12):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Zoon Safaris	USD20,000/permit	03	USD20100/ permit	Highest
2	M/S Hunting Safari	USD20,000/permit	05	USD20,100/ permit	Highest
3	M/S Himalaya Nature Tours	USD20,000/permit	03	USD20,100/ permit	Highest
4	M/S Adventure Pakistan	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20,100/ permit	Highest

ii. Sindh Ibex (12):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Zoon Safaris	USD5000/per permit	03	USD5,100/ permit	Highest
2	M/S Hunting Safari	USD5000/per permit	05	USD5,100/ permit	Highest
3	M/S Himalaya Nature Tours	USD5000/per permit	03	USD5,100/ permit	Highest
4	M/S Adventure Pakistan	USD5000/per permit	01	USD5,100/ permit	Highest

iii. Kennion Gazelle:

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Adventure Pakistan	USD5000/ permit	01	USD5,100/ permit	Highest

3. Comparative Statement for Auction of Permits of Trophy Hunting of Balochistan Urial & Ibex in Shah Noorani Community based Conservancy of Khuzdar for Hunting Season 2023-2024.

i. Blandford/Balochistan Urial (08):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Hunting Safaris	USD20,000/permit	03	USD20,050/permit	Highest
2	M/S Zoon	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20,050/permit	Highest

ii. Sindh Ibex (08):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Hunting Safari	USD5000/ permit	07	USD5,100/ permit	Highest
2	M/S Zoon Safaris	USD5000/ permit	01	USD5,100/ permit	Highest

4. Comparative Statement for Auction of Permits of Trophy Hunting of Balochistan Urial & Ibex in **Baran Lakh Community** based Conservancy of Khuzdar for Hunting Season 2023-2024.

ii. Afghan Urial (05):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Hunting Safari	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20,050/permit	Highest
2	M/S Shikar Safari Pakistan	USD20,000/permit	02	USD20,000/permit	Highest

1. Comparative Statement for Auction of Permits of Trophy Hunting of Balochistan Urial & Ibex in **Talo Band Community** based Conservancy of Gwadar for Hunting Season 2023-2024.

i. Blandford/Balochistan Urial (05):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Shikar Safari Pakistan	USD20,000/permit	04	USD20,000/permit	Highest
2	M/S Pakistan Guides	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20,000/permit	Highest

iii. Ibex (05):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Shikar Safari Pakistan	USD5000/ permit	02	USD5100/ permit	Highest
2	M/S Pakistan Guides	USD5000/ permit	01	USD5100/ permit	Highest
3	M/S Bolan Safaris	USD5000/ permit	02	USD5000/ permit	2 nd Highest

2. Comparative Statement for Auction of Permits of Trophy Hunting of Balochistan Urial & Ibex in Phore Community based Conservancy of Lasbela for Hunting Season 2023-2024.

i. Blandford/ Balochistan Urial (05):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Shikar Safari Pakistan	USD20,000/permit	03	USD20,200/permit	Highest
2	Karakurum Treks & Tours GB	USD20,000/permit	01	USD20,200/permit	Highest

ii. Ibex (05):

S.#	Name of Bidder/Outfitter	Reserved rate	No. of Permits	Rate offered in USD	Remarks
1	M/S Karakurum Treks & Tours	USD5000/ permit	01	USD5,200/ permit	Highest
2	M/S Shikar Safari Pakistan	USD5000/ permit	04	USD5000/ permit	2 nd Highest

➤ Economic Functions of Trophy hunting

The adoption of trophy hunting in Balochistan is an important initiative aimed at providing economic benefits to the local community living in or near the areas designated to Community Based Conservation. The revenue collected from trophy hunting is divided in an 80:20 proportion, with 80% provided to the community and 20% allotted to the government account. 80% of this funding is designated for enhancing community services, such as improving clean drinking water infrastructure, constructing and maintaining school buildings, recruiting teachers for community schools, providing employment opportunities as community guards, supplying labor for community projects, maintaining and developing water channels, constructing protection walls, investing in hydropower stations, and building new bridges. Trophy hunting provides immediate economic advantages to local communities by generating job possibilities, and also indirectly supports communal activities via cash donations. When residents in the area witness tangible financial, material, and intangible advantages resulting from trophy hunting activities and actively participate in making decisions about land and resource management, it promotes the formation of suitable attitudes and relationships towards both hunting and hunting for conservation purposes.

➤ Social Functions of Trophy Hunting

The level of people's movement inside the concerned conservancies has increased, enabling more opportunities for social networking and engagement with other institutions. The social functions examined in this study have enhanced the region's social capital, either via direct or indirect means. Hunting has important social purposes as it fosters the formation and maintenance of symbolic and social capital via the establishment and nurturing of ties among social groups.

➤ Ecotourism

Ecotourism is a kind of recreation or holidaying in a natural setting that prioritizes environmental, economic, ecological, and social responsibility. Ecotourism offers both social and economic benefits. Furthermore, it plays a substantial role in promoting the sustainable use of natural resources. The six conservancies in Balochistan provide picturesque landscapes with magnificent mountain vistas. The conservation efforts focused on certain ungulate species have led to an increase in the population of other animal species including birds, who have become habituated to human presence and are no longer afraid of people. Consequently, they possess a remarkable opportunity to advance the cause of ecotourism in their own areas. Regrettably, there have been no efforts undertaken to promote ecotourism in these regions.

➤ **Ungulates Population**

Balochistan harbors a diverse range of ungulate species. The enumeration of these species in protected areas is conducted using the vintage point survey approach, which was created by local communities with technical support from the wildlife department. The count survey is biannual. This research aims to ascertain the abundance of prize hunt animals during the winter rutting season. In December and January, male animals would descend to lower elevations to engage in reproductive activities with females, facilitating the process of counting them. Furthermore, the survey is carried out in the months of May and June, namely during the lambing season, with the aim of ascertaining the reproductive rate of the population.

➤ **Total Ungulate Population growth rate**

The exponential growth rate formula was used to get the total population growth rate of the Ungulates. The population figures were collected from the Wildlife Department of Balochistan and the corresponding conservancies. The exponential growth rate is positive, suggesting that the entire population of Ungulates is increasing.

Recommendations

- Establishment of more Protected Areas with new targeted species.
- Creation of Endowment Fund for Trophy Hunting.
- Promotion of Local Trophy Hunting.
- Online Setup of Bidding for the convenience of International Trophy Hunters
- Establishment of Committee at District Level to monitor the distribution of incentives and development work.
- Technological based surveys.
- For conserving the biodiversity, organizing, boosting, and empowering the capacity of the local communities is necessary
- Strong legislation and framing of a financial framework are needed, which should be community conducive.
- The distributional ratio of the hunt fee among communities should be revised, and the local wildlife department should make sure that hunts should not only be carried out in one village it should also be carried out in other towns where hunt animals are present
- The terms of the partnership signed between communities and the wildlife department should be revised in three years
- The 20% of the fee which goes to the treasury of the government should be given to the local wildlife department to enhance its capacity
- The hunting quota should be increased to five hunts each year from two hunts as the hunt animals are present in the areas
- The Community representatives should be for five years, and after five years new representative should be selected or elected
- Research based study in each conservancy to know the perception of local communities regarding Trophy Hunting Programs.
- Involvement of District Administration to ensure security of hunters.
- Recurrent Surveys in the Conservancies.
- Implementation of projects for mitigation of Climate Change and Biodiversity.
- Campaigns for Zoonotic Disease Control.
- Livestock Vaccination
- Awareness Rising.

Conclusion

The Trophy Hunting Program in Balochistan's community-based conservancies has demonstrated effectiveness in species conservation by regulating hunting and generating revenue, which incentivizes local communities to protect and manage wildlife populations. It also generates significant income for local communities through trophy hunting, promoting economic benefits and contributing to community development. By fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility towards wildlife conservation, the program supports conservation efforts and habitat protection. When managed properly, trophy hunting can be a viable strategy for balancing human needs with wildlife conservation, promoting coexistence and sustainable use of natural resources.

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